

The Interaction of Sign Language and Gesture in Theatre Performance

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Artistic and metalinguistic uses of language, as in poetry and language games, manipulate aspects of linguistic structure for aesthetic effect or entertainment. By extending language beyond its normal boundaries, such manipulations can reveal much about underlying linguistic form and communicative function (Bagemihl 1995, Christen 1998). Similarly, the artistic use of the body by deaf actors in our Sign Language Theatre Laboratory goes well beyond the gestural repertoire that typically accompanies speech or sign to reveal the full gestural potential of the human body.

In this study we show that the accepted categorization of gestures (McNeill 1992) is exploited in a unique way in visual theatre that combines signs with gesture and mime. By artfully blurring the line between language and gesture, theatrical performance by signers casts each into high relief, and reveals an expanded repertoire of visible communicative combinations.

Our videotaped data include an improvised restaurant scene in which the waitress describes the daily specials. In the actress' creative and amusing depiction, we find: (1) **the full continuum** from language to gesture (McNeill, 1992; Kendon, 2005) – gesticulation, pantomime, emblems, and sign language (e.g., see Figure (1a,b) for a sequence of pantomime and a lexical sign in describing the same event); and (2) use of different parts of the body to produce a range of gestural and linguistic dimensions **simultaneously**. The result is a medium that merges communicative with corporeal compositionality.

Figure (2) below exemplifies a complex, simultaneous, compositional bodily expression. (a) The actress' right hand is configured to represent a linguistic classifier for a flat object (a steak). (b) Her left hand pantomimes flipping the meat in a pan. (c) On her face is an iconic mouth gesture for a visual 'sound' – the impact each time the meat hits the pan. This is an example of the way in which the roles of mouth and hand in speech are reversed in the iconic gestures accompanying sign language (Sandler 2009). (d) At the same time, the body swings to enhance the effect of the motion conveyed by the hands.

This body movement represents a new non-manual gesture category that arises from our data -- **Enhancement Body Beats (EBBs)** -- in which the body mirrors and magnifies the action of the manual gesture. As rhythmic movements aligned with the prosodic patterns of signing, EBBs resemble manual *beats* (McNeill 1992, Gullberg 1998), and are another switch in the roles of different parts of the body from those of spoken language. The hands convey the content of the message, and the body conveys the beats.

These and other examples in our analysis of an artistic medium that is exclusively visual go beyond the familiar gestural continuum to manifest a compositional medley of communicative actions.

Figure 1: (a) Pantomime 'fishing' and (b) lexical sign FISH

(a)

(b)

Figure 2: Simultaneous bodily expression of gesture dimensions

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